

Enteric Methane and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review and Technical Guidance

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

June 30, 2025

ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY NETWORK FOR CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

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INTRODUCTION

Enteric methane emissions from ruminant livestock are a major contributor to agricultural greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, particularly in beef and dairy systems. As methane has over 80 times the warming potential of CO₂ over a 20-year horizon, targeting methane reduction is a highly impactful climate mitigation strategy. The USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) is well-positioned to guide farmers toward adopting practices that are both environmentally effective and economically viable.

This synthesis provides a science-based assessment of three key strategies for methane reduction through feed and health interventions. In addition, two interventions with highest potential in the near future are also included:

Key strategies for methane reduction:

- 3-Nitrooxypropanol (Bovaer®)
- Tannins
- Dietary lipids

Future interventions:

- Bromoform-containing additives
- Methane-reducing vaccines

We conclude with a partial economic feasibility assessment, focusing on the recommended additives.

3-NITROOXYPROPANOL (BOVAER®)

Bovaer® is a small molecule feed additive, known chemically as 3-nitrooxypropanol (3-NOP), that inhibits the enzyme methyl-coenzyme M reductase, essential for methanogenesis in the rumen. A comprehensive meta-analysis by Kebreab et al. (2023) showed that in dairy cattle the average reduction potential was about 32%. 3-NOP reduced both total methane production and methane yield (g CH₄/kg DMI), with minimal impact on dry matter intake and milk yield when included at recommended levels. 3-NOP is the only FDA approved feed additive in the US but only for dairy cattle. It is expected for similar approval to follow for beef cattle as well.

In beef cattle, a meta-analysis is being conducted by Kebreab et al. (2025, in progress). The analysis combined data from 17 studies covering various breeds, diets, and geographic regions. Across all studies, 3-NOP reduced methane production by an average of 36.2% and methane yield (g CH₄/kg DMI) by 26.4%. These reductions were statistically significant and robust across different study designs. The analysis

found no significant effect of 3-NOP on dry matter intake, average daily gain, or feed conversion ratio, indicating that methane mitigation was achieved without compromising growth performance. A linear dose-response relationship was observed, where higher inclusion rates of 3-NOP corresponded to greater methane reductions.

Together, the findings from these two meta-analyses establish a consistent and strong effect of 3-NOP in reducing enteric methane emissions in beef and dairy cattle. The additive's effectiveness is dose-dependent and has been demonstrated across different diets, measurement techniques, and animal categories. Importantly, both analyses underscore that 3-NOP achieves significant methane reductions without impairing intake or productivity, making it a reliable tool for enteric methane mitigation in confined cattle systems.

TANNINS

Tannins are naturally occurring polyphenolic compounds found in many plants. They inhibit methane production by suppressing protozoa, methanogens, and fiber-digesting microbes, and by reducing hydrogen availability in the rumen. A meta-analysis conducted as part of this project by Souza et al. (2025) assessed 25 peer-reviewed in vivo studies on enteric methane emissions, productivity, and digestibility in dairy and beef cattle. The analysis quantifies both the mitigation potential and any associated trade-offs across species and production systems.

In dairy cattle, tannins were found to reduce methane yield by an average of 10.3% and methane intensity (grams of methane per kilogram of milk) by approximately 9.4%. These reductions suggest that tannins can improve emissions efficiency per unit of milk produced. However, this environmental benefit comes with modest productivity trade-offs. Dry matter intake decreased by about 2.7%, and milk yield showed a similar reduction of 2.2%. These results indicate that while tannins are effective at reducing methane, their application in dairy systems must be carefully managed to avoid compromising performance, especially under high inclusion rates or poorly matched dietary conditions.

In beef cattle, tannin supplementation resulted in a greater average reduction in methane yield of 12.6% and a decrease in methane intensity per kilogram of weight gain by 11.8%. Importantly, beef systems were more tolerant to tannin inclusion: there was no significant effect on average daily gain, and dry matter intake remained largely unaffected. This resilience makes tannins particularly well-suited for beef production, including semi-intensive and extensive systems, where delivery of daily feed additives like 3-NOP is not always feasible. The lack of productivity loss in beef systems enhances the appeal of tannins as a mitigation strategy that does not require complex infrastructure or high-cost inputs.

While tannins had some negative effects on fiber digestibility, particularly neutral detergent fiber, the impact on crude protein digestibility was generally neutral or slightly positive depending on the type of tannin and overall diet composition. Taken together, the findings position tannins as a viable feed additive with moderate methane mitigation potential, especially for beef systems. In dairy systems, their adoption is more sensitive to dosage and formulation. However, their relatively low cost, natural origin, and compatibility with existing feeding practices make them an important part of the broader methane mitigation portfolio for livestock.

DIETARY LIPIDS

Dietary lipid supplementation reduces methane through multiple mechanisms: dilution of fermentable carbohydrates, suppression of methanogens and protozoa, and provision of alternative hydrogen sinks.

A second-order meta-analysis conducted through the Enteric Methane Technical Working Group by Ramirez-Agudelo and Kebreab (2025), synthesized 13 meta-analyses (~184 primary studies). The results indicate that lipid supplementation reduces methane production by an average of 12.4%, with methane yield (grams of methane per kilogram of dry matter intake) declining by approximately 8.2%. This demonstrates a moderate reduction in emissions per unit of feed consumed, though less dramatic than that achieved by synthetic additives such as 3-NOP. The study also highlights that the mitigation effect varies depending on lipid source, inclusion level, and baseline diet composition. Notably, long-chain fatty acids from sources like canola oil and coconut oil showed consistent reductions, while high inclusion levels (>6% of diet DM) risked adverse impacts on fiber digestibility and feed intake.

In dairy cattle, lipid supplementation consistently lowered methane emissions without severely compromising milk yield when formulated correctly. However, at higher inclusion rates, reductions in dry matter intake and milk fat concentration were occasionally observed, emphasizing the importance of balancing emission reductions with productivity goals. In beef cattle, lipid inclusion showed similar methane mitigation, especially in feedlot settings where ration control is feasible. Effects on growth performance were generally neutral, with some studies even reporting improved feed efficiency due to the higher energy density of lipid-enriched diets.

Dietary lipids offer a modest but reliable methane mitigation strategy suitable for both dairy and beef systems, particularly where controlled feeding is possible. While the average mitigation effect is smaller than that of specialized additives like 3-NOP, lipids benefit from already being integrated into many commercial rations for energy supplementation. The results support their role as a complementary mitigation strategy, especially in systems where additional methane reductions are needed without major infrastructure changes. Adoption, however, must consider feed cost, inclusion limits, and the nutritional balancing of rations to avoid unintended productivity losses.

Details of the study are provided in Ramirez-Agudelo and Kebreab, 2025.

BROMOFORM-BASED FEED ADDITIVES

Bromoform (CHBr_3), the active compound in *Asparagopsis* red seaweed, blocks methanogenesis by inhibiting key enzymes in archaea. A meta-analysis, supported in part by the Enteric Methane Technical Working Group, by Kebreab et al. (2025) found the following results from the use of bromoform as a feed additive.

In dairy cattle, at an average dose of approximately 28.3 mg bromoform per kg of dry matter, methane production was reduced by 47.3%, methane yield by 43.3%, and methane intensity by 39.0%. However,

this mitigation came with trade-offs in intake and productivity. Dry matter intake decreased by an estimated 6.45%, and milk production was reduced by 4.60% on average at the same dose. Diet composition also influenced efficacy: higher starch content enhanced methane reduction, while elevated levels of neutral detergent fiber (NDF) diminished the effect. Furthermore, the form of the additive mattered—oil-based carriers tended to produce more pronounced methane reductions than biomass, and studies using respiration chambers reported greater reductions than other methods.

In beef cattle, the same average bromoform dose (≈ 28.3 mg/kg DM) produced slightly stronger methane mitigation than in dairy systems. Dry matter intake was reduced by 3.26%, though no significant adverse effects on daily gain were reported. As in dairy, diet composition influenced the mitigation effect, i.e., greater dietary starch enhanced CH_4 suppression, while NDF had a dampening effect. These results suggest that CHBr_3 additives are highly effective in reducing methane emissions in beef cattle with comparatively minor impacts on intake, making them particularly promising for controlled feeding systems.

Currently, no CHBr_3 -based additives are approved for commercial use in the U.S. Regulatory pathways, including residue safety in milk and meat, must be clarified. However, synthetic stabilized products are under active development, and multiple companies are pursuing FDA and European Food Safety Authority approvals. This approach may be transformative once approved for use, particularly in high-efficiency systems where dietary precision and cost-justification are feasible.

METHANE-REDUCING VACCINES

Vaccines are an innovative strategy that could shift the paradigm of methane mitigation, especially in extensive grazing systems where feed-based approaches are challenging.

A review of existing studies indicates:

- In vitro reductions of 12–40% in methane when using sera or antibodies from vaccinated animals,
- The most promising in vivo study (Muntari et al., 2024) showed a significant reduction in methane yield without impacting DMI or average daily gain,
- Other in vivo trials have shown mixed results, and several studies report no effect.

The concept is based on immunizing animals against key methanogenic archaea. Antibodies are transferred to the rumen via saliva. However, challenges include antigen stability, variable immune responses, need for boosters, and scale-up logistics.

This approach is still in the early stages but holds long-term promise. It may be especially relevant for cow–calf operations, rangeland systems, and smallholders, where recurring feed-based inputs are impractical. Investment in R&D is needed to establish efficacy, safety, and regulatory pathways.

ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY FOR RECOMMENDED ADDITIVES

A partial budget analysis (Ferreira et al., 2025) was conducted through the Enteric Methane Technical Working Group. The economic feasibility and adoption potential of three feed additives (3-NOP, tannins, and lipids) was carried out for reducing enteric methane emissions in U.S. dairy and beef production. Their mitigation efficacy, cost-effectiveness, and adoption barriers in different production systems, including confined dairies, feedlots, and cow-calf operations were evaluated.

3-NOP (Bovaer®) is the most commercially viable methane-reducing feed additive, with the potential to reduce methane emissions by 32% in lactating dairy cows (Kebreab et al., 2023). The cost of 3-NOP is estimated at \$0.44 per cow per day. Despite its proven efficacy, adoption remains limited due to its high cost. We suggest that carbon credits or value-added product premiums could make 3-NOP economically viable, particularly for high-efficiency systems such as dairy farms. However, in extensive systems like grazing operations, its use remains impractical without long-acting formulations or alternative delivery methods.

Tannins are a low-cost option for methane reduction, offering about 10% reductions in methane emissions in both dairy and beef systems (Souza et al., 2025). At a cost of \$0.03 per cow per day, tannins represent a more affordable option compared to 3-NOP. However, their effectiveness varies based on

dosage and feed composition. Tannins have negative effects on dry matter intake and milk yield at higher inclusion rates, which may limit their adoption. Despite these concerns, tannins could be a viable option in systems that already use plant-based feed additives.

Lipids are another promising methane-reducing strategy, with potential reductions of 12%–14% in methane emissions, depending on the oil and fat content in the diet (Ramirez-Agudelo et al., 2025). The cost of incorporating oils and lipids into dairy diets is estimated at \$0.70 per cow per day. While this cost is higher than that of tannins, lipids can be integrated into existing dairy and beef diets without major adjustments. However, the impact of lipids on feed intake and milk fat content needs to be considered, as it may affect overall productivity. Lipids have moderate adoption potential, particularly in feedlot beef operations.

In conclusion, 3-NOP offers the highest potential for near-term adoption in confined dairy and beef systems, but its high cost remains a barrier without external incentives like carbon credits. Tannins offer a more affordable alternative with moderate effectiveness, but their adoption may be limited by impacts on productivity. Lipids offer methane reduction benefits but require careful management of dietary effects. There is a need for financial mechanisms to support the adoption of these feed additives and calls for increased research to improve their cost-effectiveness and integration into broader livestock systems.

A full report of the economic analysis conducted has been provided to NRCS (Ferreira et al., 2025).

REFERENCES

- Ferreira, F., Place, S., & Reis, I. (2025). Economic feasibility of methane-reducing feed additives. Partial report. (Unpublished internal analysis)
- Kebreab, E., Bannink, A., Pressman, E. M., Walker, N., Karagiannis, A., van Gastelen, S., & Dijkstra, J. (2023). A meta-analysis of effects of 3-nitrooxypropanol on methane production, yield, and intensity in dairy cattle. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 106(2): 927–936.
<https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2022-22211>
- Kebreab, E., Pressman, E. M., Ramirez-Agudelo, J. F., Bannink, A., van Gastelen, S., & Dijkstra, J. (Draft 2025). A meta-analysis of effects of seaweed and other bromoform-containing feed ingredients on methane production, yield, and intensity in cattle. *bioRxiv*.
<https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.05.17.654669>.
- Muntari, M., Arciero, B. R., Kuhn, C., Mulcock, K., Smith, D., Poliakiwski, B., ... & Dunn, M. R. (2024). PSV-10 Vaccination of beef cattle to reduce enteric methane emissions. *Journal of Animal Science*, 102(Supplement_3), 512-513.
- Ramirez-Agudelo, J. F., & Kebreab, E. (Draft 2025). A second-order meta-analysis on the effect of dietary lipids on enteric methane emission. (Unpublished draft)
- Souza, V. C., et al. (Draft 2025). Impact of tannin-based additives on animal performance and enteric methane emissions in beef and dairy cattle: a meta-analysis. University of São Paulo & University of California, Davis. (Unpublished draft).

Appendix: Science Recommendations

RESEARCH

More research trials are needed to identify potential anti-methanogenic solutions and to better understand the safety profile and effectiveness potential of anti-methanogenic feed additives and vaccines to reduce enteric methane emissions including long-term studies and stacking of solutions.

POLICY

There are significant policy barriers to federal approval and market availability of anti-methanogenic feed additives and vaccines, including the need for a clearly defined FDA review and approval process. A rigorous, standardized federal review process must assess product safety for animals, product safety for users, product safety for consumers, product effectiveness, impacts on productivity, and other relevant environmental impacts. Methods for measuring methane emissions must be validated.

MEASUREMENT, DATA COLLECTION, AND DATA ACCESS

STANDARDIZATION OF METHANE MEASUREMENT PROTOCOLS

Uniform, transparent, and reproducible protocols are needed for measuring methane emissions across studies and regions. These should include specifications for animal type, dose, dietary context, duration of exposure, measurement techniques (e.g., respiration chambers, GreenFeed, tracers), and co-measured traits (e.g., feed intake, productivity, manure emissions). Currently the measurement methods are too expensive for wider adoption, there are challenges with accuracy and reliability of data produced, and the methodologies are largely inconsistent to allow for effective comparison of results.

DATA COLLECTION ON ADDITIVE DEPLOYMENT

There is a critical need to document actual application practices of feed additives on farms e.g., inclusion rate, duration, mixing methods, and compliance because these impact mitigation potential and model accuracy.

EXPANDED ADDITIVE MONITORING VIA NOVEL TECHNOLOGIES

The use of emerging tools (e.g., portable gas analyzers, sensor-based intake monitors, wearable methane measurement devices, automated additive delivery systems) can enable broader, more continuous monitoring of methane emissions and additive effects at scale.

GHG ACCOUNTING AND MODELING

CONSISTENT SYSTEM BOUNDARIES

To assess the net GHG effect of feed additives, models must consistently account for on-farm emissions

(enteric, manure) and off-farm emissions (additive production, transport). Clear boundary definitions are essential to avoid double counting or underestimating impacts.

IMPROVED ADDITIVE-SPECIFIC MODEL INPUTS

Process-based and empirical models require robust, additive-specific inputs such as mitigation potential (% CH₄ reduction per dose), duration of effect, and possible impacts on feed intake and animal productivity. These parameters should be stratified by region, diet, species, and production stage.

INTEGRATION OF FEED ADDITIVE EFFECTS INTO WHOLE-FARM MODELS

To better understand trade-offs and co-benefits (e.g., productivity, manure methane shifts), the effects of 3-NOP, tannins, and lipids must be fully integrated into existing carbon and nitrogen cycle models used for livestock systems.

DECISION SUPPORT ANALYSIS AND TOOLS

FARM-FACING TOOLS FOR ADDITIVE DECISION-MAKING

Decision-support tools should be developed or adapted to help producers evaluate whether and how to adopt feed additives. Tools should consider additive availability, compatibility with feed rations, projected emissions reductions, return on investment, and possible productivity changes.

SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS AND META-ANALYSES TO GUIDE PRACTICE

High-quality systematic reviews and meta-analyses are critical to synthesize additive performance across diverse conditions. These reviews should form the scientific basis for:

- Practice standards (e.g., NRCS Conservation Practice Standards),
- Incentive program design,
- Regulatory frameworks (carbon markets), and National GHG inventory updates.

For the feed additives recommended, there is already a meta-analysis on 3NOP. Two new meta-analyses are nearly completed as part of this project and will be delivered to NRCS upon completion.

Appendix: Field Guides

Field Guide: Using 3-NOP to Reduce Methane Emissions in Dairy and Beef Cattle

WHAT IS 3-NOP?

3-Nitrooxypropanol (3-NOP) is a targeted feed additive that reduces methane emissions from ruminants. It works by inhibiting the enzyme methyl-coenzyme M reductase, which is responsible for the final step in methane production in the rumen. 3-NOP does not harm beneficial microbes and has been widely studied in both dairy and beef cattle.

EFFECTIVENESS

In dairy cattle:

- Reduces methane emissions by 30–40%.
- Has no significant impact on milk yield or dry matter intake at recommended doses.
- Works reliably across a variety of diet types.

In beef cattle:

- Reduces methane production by 36.2% and methane yield by 26.4% on average.
- Maintains dry matter intake and daily weight gain.
- Shows a dose-dependent response: higher inclusion = greater reduction.

HOW TO CALCULATE METHANE REDUCTION

To estimate how effective 3-NOP is in your herd, use the following formula (from Kebreab et al., 2023):

Change (%) in methane production = $-32.4 - 0.282 \times (3\text{-NOP dose} - 70.5) + 0.915 \times (\text{NDF} - 32.9) + 3.080 \times (\text{crude fat} - 4.2)$,

where 3-NOP = 3-nitroxypropanol dose (mg/kg of DM), and NDF and crude fat are in % DM.

FEEDING AND USE

- Formulation: Included in mineral premix or concentrate; compatible with TMR systems.
- Effective Dose: Typically 40–80 mg per kg DMI.
- Feeding Frequency: Must be fed daily (twice if possible). No long-lasting effects once withdrawn.

- Storage: Store in a cool, dry place. Avoid exposure to heat and moisture.

WHEN TO USE IT

- ✓ Feedlots and confined beef operations
- ✓ Dairy farms with controlled feeding systems
- ✗ Not recommended for grazing herds without feed delivery infrastructure

PROS

- ✓ High methane reduction—scientifically proven
- ✓ No loss in productivity—supports milk and growth performance
- ✓ Effective across diets—high forage or concentrate systems

CONS

- ⚠ Needs daily feeding—not suited to pasture-based systems
- ⚠ No residual effect—benefits stop when feeding stops
- ⚠ Requires mixing accuracy—dosing must be consistent

SUMMARY

3-NOP offers a reliable, science-backed solution to reduce enteric methane in cattle. By incorporating it into daily rations at the right dose, producers can achieve substantial emissions reductions without sacrificing animal performance. Use the efficacy equation to track progress and guide ration formulation.

Field Guide: Using Dietary Lipids to Reduce Methane Emissions in Dairy and Beef Cattle

WHAT ARE DIETARY LIPIDS?

Dietary lipids, such as oils, fats, and oilseeds, are energy-dense feed ingredients that can reduce enteric methane emissions in ruminants. They act by reducing fiber digestion, altering rumen fermentation patterns, and decreasing hydrogen availability for methanogens. Common lipid sources include canola oil, linseed, cottonseed, and distillers' grains.

EFFECTIVENESS

In dairy cattle:

- Average reduction in methane production: 10.7%
- Average reduction in methane yield: 9.8%
- Milk yield generally unaffected at low to moderate lipid inclusion rates (<5% of diet DM).

In beef cattle:

- Average reduction in methane production: 14.6%
- Average reduction in methane yield: 13.0%
- No significant reduction in average daily gain or feed intake up to moderate inclusion levels.

HOW TO CALCULATE METHANE REDUCTION

To estimate the expected reduction (%) at different dietary ether extract (EE) levels relative to the 3% baseline:

Change (%) in methane production = $-30.4 \times (1 - \exp(-0.2 \times (EE - 3.0)))$.

where EE = amount of lipids (ether extract) in % DM.

FEEDING AND USE

- Formulation: Oils, oilseeds, or lipid-rich byproducts (e.g., dried distillers' grains).
- Dose: Most effective at 2–6% of diet dry matter.
- Feeding Systems: Suitable for both TMR and grain-based systems; limited use in pasture-only systems.
- Monitor fat levels: Excess fat (>6–7% total diet DM) may impair fiber digestion and reduce feed intake.

WHEN TO USE IT

- ✓ Confinement systems with controlled feeding
- ✓ Ration-balancing strategies that include energy supplementation
- ✗ Avoid high-fat inclusion in high-forage or pasture-based systems without adaptation

Pros

- ✓ Readily available as feed ingredients
- ✓ Consistent methane reduction in both dairy and beef systems
- ✓ Energy-dense source that may improve diet formulation

Cons

- ⚠ Excessive fat can impair rumen function and digestibility
- ⚠ Variable responses depending on lipid type and saturation
- ⚠ May affect milk fat percentage at high inclusion rates in dairy cows

SUMMARY

Dietary lipids are a practical and effective strategy to reduce methane emissions from cattle. They offer moderate emission reductions and can be integrated into existing feeding programs. Proper formulation and attention to total fat intake are key to achieving benefits without compromising productivity.

Field Guide: Using Tannins to Reduce Methane Emissions in Dairy and Beef Cattle

WHAT ARE TANNINS?

Tannins are naturally occurring plant compounds found in many forages, trees, and legumes. They have been shown to reduce enteric methane emissions by binding to proteins and interfering with microbial activity in the rumen. Tannins vary widely in chemical structure and potency depending on their source, and their effects on digestion and performance depend on dose and type.

EFFECTIVENESS

In dairy cattle:

- Average reduction in methane yield of 8.7%.
- Minimal to no negative effects on milk production when included at appropriate levels.
- Greater efficacy observed with condensed tannins from quebracho and sainfoin.

In beef cattle:

- Average methane yield reduction of 10.9%.
- Typically no negative effects on weight gain or feed intake at moderate doses.
- Effective in both pasture and feedlot systems depending on delivery method.

HOW TO CALCULATE METHANE REDUCTION

To estimate how effective tannins are in your herd, use the following formula:

$$\text{Change (\%)} \text{ in methane production} = -10.3 - 0.001 \times (\text{Tannin dose} - 11,542).$$

where Tannin dose is expressed in mg/kg of DM.

FEEDING AND USE

- Formulation: Can be included as part of forage (e.g., sainfoin) or as an extract (e.g., chestnut or quebracho powder).
- Dose: Effectiveness observed at 1–3% of dietary dry matter.

- Feeding Systems: Suitable for both pasture and mixed feeding systems.
- Avoid overfeeding: High doses (>5% DM) may reduce feed intake and fiber digestibility.

WHEN TO USE IT

- ✓ Grazing systems with access to tannin-rich legumes or supplements
- ✓ Mixed rations where tannin extracts can be added precisely
- ✗ Avoid in high doses without evaluating fiber digestibility impacts

Pros

- ✓ Naturally derived and acceptable in many production systems
- ✓ Suitable for pasture-based operations
- ✓ Moderate methane reductions without loss in productivity at proper doses

Cons

- ⚠ Efficacy is lower than other additives like 3-NOP or bromoform
- ⚠ Overfeeding can reduce digestibility and intake
- ⚠ Variability in tannin type and content across plant sources

SUMMARY

Tannins offer a natural, accessible method for reducing methane emissions in both dairy and beef systems. Although their efficacy is modest compared to synthetic additives, they are particularly valuable in pasture-based operations. Correct dosing and proper selection of tannin source are key to achieving benefits without compromising animal productivity.